

UZBEKISTAN ON THE THRESHOLD OF ACCESSION TO THE WTO

Sayidkomil Bekpulat ugli Ibodullaev

Lecturer at the Tashkent State University of Law

Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan

(email: s.ibodullayev@tsul.uz)

Annotation: The international organization that regulates the rules of international trade is the World Trade Organization (WTO). This article provides a brief overview of the process of the Republic of Uzbekistan's accession to the WTO, examines the advantages and disadvantages of membership in this organization, analyzes the benefits and challenges ahead for Uzbekistan against the background of the accession process

Key words: WTO, Uzbekistan, economic globalization, international trade, accession, investments

Today, the further development of the state and the well-being of population is difficult to imagine without active foreign trade activity against the backdrop of the process of economic globalization, which has covered every sphere of life of modern world community. Foreign trade is designed to serve to increase the country's performance in trade with foreign countries and plays a key role in integrating into international trade.

The World Trade Organization (WTO), which was founded on January 1, 1995, sets itself the goal of liberalizing international trade and regulating trade relations between its members, whose number today has reached **164 countries** of the world. Thus, almost **99 %** of international trade is carried out within the framework of the trade turnover of the member countries of this organization.¹

¹ WTO official statistics, https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/whatis_e/tif_e/org6_e.htm

Realizing such a volume of world trade carried out according to the rules of the WTO, it would be difficult to imagine Uzbekistan as an active participant in the modern world community without membership in this organization. Currently, the Republic of Uzbekistan is consistently implementing economic reforms based on market principles, expanding the share of private sector, strengthening economic stability and increasing the attractiveness of the republic for foreign investors.²

Of the post-Soviet countries, only Azerbaijan, Belarus, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan still have observer status in the WTO. Moreover, factors such as the search for new markets, attraction of foreign direct investment and strengthening the competitiveness of local producers dictate to meet the new realities of economic globalization.

The history of the beginning of process of Uzbekistan's accession to the WTO goes back to the recent past, 1994, when on December 21 the first working group for our country was created, the last meeting of which was held in 2005 and since then this process has been suspended. The process under consideration was resumed in 2018, when a state **working group on WTO accession** was created and the corresponding **road map**³ was adopted. It reflected measures aimed at preparing the necessary documentation and adapting national legislation. During his interview to the Japanese business publication Nikkei Asian Review, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan HE Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted that the country will accelerate economic and democratic reforms and will strive to join

² Сиражиддинов Н. Либерализация внешнеторговых операций конкурентоспособность национальной экономики // Экономическое обозрение. Ташкент, – 2017. – №11. – С. 67–72.

³ Order of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Roadmap for enhancing cooperation with the WTO for 2020", online available at: https://regulation.gov.uz/ru/document/16080#_ftn1

the organization as soon as possible.⁴

The process of Uzbekistan's accession to the WTO can be conditionally divided into the following stages:

- 1) **2019-2021** – adaptation period of the economy to new market mechanisms;
- 2) **2022-2025** – liberalization of foreign trade policy, consideration of the issue of compliance with WTO norms of non-tariff trade barriers;
- 3) **2026-2030** – development of export-oriented trade.

The activity of WTO member states is based on the commitment to the principles of (1) **most favored nation treatment** and (2) **national treatment**.⁵ The first involves the provision of equal conditions to all foreign trading partners and the prevention of any discrimination. Accordingly, the second requires the provision of equal conditions and trade requirements for local producers on a par with foreign ones. Within the framework of the WTO, there is a single set of rules, in case of violation of which, states can submit their applications to the judicial **authority (Dispute Settlement Body)** to resolve the legal differences that have arisen. All states participate in the adoption of certain decisions and the **consensus method** is used, which is one of the distinguishing features in the work of this organization.

When asked why Uzbekistan wants to join the WTO, we would like to emphasize that a member country of the organization inspires more confidence among foreign partners, especially among foreign investors than, say, a non-member country, since in such countries for doing business *stability*,

⁴ <https://asia.nikkei.com/Editor-s-Picks/Interview/Uzbekistan-plans-over-6bn-in-joint-projects-with-Japan>

⁵ Article I and III of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) 1994

predictability and compliance with the requirements of uniform norms play a decisive role. Accession to the WTO will once again prove that an already renewed Uzbekistan has appeared on the international arena, which is ready for open business.

Among experts and representatives of the public of Uzbekistan, there are still heated discussions about whether it is worth joining the WTO and what it will give in general. On this issue, it should be noted that the benefits derived from WTO membership will depend on the member countries themselves, on how much the state's exports can become a driver of its economic growth.

As Mr. James Wolfensohn, former President of the World Bank, noted, in order for economic globalization and international trade to contribute to economic development, equality and well-being of the population, countries need to provide the following components:

- good governance at the national level;
- further reduction of trade barriers;
- more development assistance;
- better international cooperation and global regulation of economic globalization and international trade.⁶

It is also worth mentioning the criticism of the WTO. It has been accused of giving priority to rich countries, in particular transnational corporations (TNCs); even as a member of the organization, countries are not protected from the imposition of politically motivated economic sanctions unilaterally; also safety, health and environmental issues are increasingly being neglected in favor of additional business benefits. Of course, improperly implemented trade liberalization can drag the country into poverty, and full openness is a big risk

⁶ James Wolfensohn 'Responding to the Challenges of Globalization', Remarks to the G-20 Conference, available at www.worldbank.org/html/extdr/extme/jdwsp111701.htm.

from external shocks.⁷

In particular, among the “**globalophobes**” the following number of issues is of concern, which may be, to one degree or another, subject to the negative impact of international trade:

- work and wages;
- state of the global and local ecosystems;
- poverty and hunger;
- economic development of developing countries;
- social, labor, health and safety issues;
- livelihoods of small producers;
- cultural identity and diversity;
- national sovereignty and democratic processes.⁸

What benefits can Uzbekistan get from WTO membership?

Firstly, it will provide access to foreign (export) markets for domestically produced products. If earlier we supplied products to countries with which we had bilateral agreements, then after joining the organization, we will provide new markets for local producers;

Secondly, as a member of the WTO, favorable conditions will be created in Uzbekistan for a significant improvement in the quality and competitiveness of domestic goods and services against the backdrop of a large influx of imports into the country. It is clear that local producers will be forced to produce products according to completely different requirements and standards, in case of non-

⁷ J. Stiglitz, ‘Addressing Developing Country Priorities and Needs in the Millennium Round’ Seattle, the WTO and the Future of the Multilateral Trading System, Harvard University Press, 2000, at 53-55.

⁸ Peter Van den Bossche, Werner Zdouc, ‘The Law and Policy of the World Trade Organization’ Cambridge University Press, 2013, at 14-15.

compliance with which, they risk losing their positions to importers;

Thirdly, accession will serve as a good impetus for bringing national legislation in line with WTO rules. This will create an appropriate legislative framework, according to which the norms of legislation will be brought under the common denominator of uniform rules for conducting foreign trade activities on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Fourthly, WTO membership will serve to create and improve a favorable climate for attracting foreign investment to Uzbekistan;

Fifthly, it will create additional jobs;

Sixth, membership in the WTO creates the conditions for more active participation in the development of rules for international trade, taking into account their national interests. Each member of the organization has equal rights when making decisions, if even the least developed state expresses a point of view that differs from the opinion of the majority, then this decision is not subject to adoption;

Seventh, accession to the WTO will definitely improve the international image of Uzbekistan, give positive signals for further improvement of positions in international rankings.

However, it should be noted that a number of complex works have to be completed before joining the WTO, which will also affect the duration of the process of our country's accession:

- it is necessary to ensure the stability of national legislation;
- coordinate compliance with its requirements;
- appropriate administrative, customs and tax reforms are required;
- it is necessary to work on the state of the infrastructure;
- strengthen the fight against corruption;
- establish a system for training WTO-specialists.

Summarizing the above, we can say that accession to the WTO for

Uzbekistan at the current stage of development is an **objective necessity**, and will play a powerful accelerator to unlock its economic potential. Uzbekistan has already submitted its **Memorandum on Foreign Trade** and answered a number of questions on it. On the part of the leadership of the republic, a set of measures is being implemented to join the organization as soon as possible, which, in turn, we believe should happen in the near future.

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